

ANALYSIS ON DATA WITH FATIGUE 1-2

Number of trials per stimulus mode					
	0	100	140	180	Total
None	15	-	-	-	15
AudioOnly	-	20	21	11	52
VisualsOnly	-	23	17	14	54
Both	-	16	22	19	57
Total	15	59	60	44	178

Stimuli type and performance

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: correctNormalized

ANOVA correctNormalized~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.367	0.777	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasStimulusTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
0.9981548	0.9963345	0.079819	0.937

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasVisualTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
0.9901633	1.0109868	-0.93875	0.3495

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasAudioTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
1.0016592	0.9922232	0.44769	0.655

Stimuli tempo and performance

Parameter: tempo | Variable: correctNormalized | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo		
F	p	
3.461	0.0176	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
1.249	0.296	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
1.936	0.155	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
2.042	0.14	

TukeyHSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p	adj
100-0	-0.04392598	-0.1480222	0.0601703	0.6933014
140-0	0.02106016	-0.0828601	0.1249805	0.9527778
180-0	0.03692555	-0.0707073	0.1445584	0.8100956
140-100	0.06498614	-0.0010167	0.1309890	0.0553732
180-100	0.08085153	0.0091452	0.1525578	0.0202134
180-140	0.01586539	-0.0555852	0.0873159	0.9391503

Stimuli type and time estimation

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception)

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
2.102	0.102	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasStimulusTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
0.0125998	0.0981775	-1.0014	0.3321

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasVisualTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
-0.0046747	0.0603780	-1.7062	0.09033

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasAudioTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
0.0405917	-0.0130154	1.4388	0.1524

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.608	0.611	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasStimulusTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
0.1828661	0.2113972	-0.42091	0.6799

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasVisualTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
0.1805191	0.1931421	-0.49603	0.6208

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasAudioTrial			
mean	Has-No	t	p
0.1927911	0.1733900	0.7794	0.4371

Stimuli tempo and time estimation

Parameter: tempo | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception) | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo		
F	p	
1.383	0.25	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.533	0.59	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.204	0.816	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
1.39	0.258	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo		
F	p	
0.268	0.848	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.067	0.936	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.219	0.804	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
0.16	0.853	

Stimuli type and time judgment

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~classes				
chi-2	df	p		
7.2264	3	0.06502		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasStimulusTrial			
W	p	mean Has	mean Not
1548.5	0.0732		
3.196319	2.66667		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasAudioTrial			
W	p	mean Has	mean Not
3971.5	0.5089		
3.201835	3.072464		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasVisualTrial			
W	p	mean Has	mean Not
4455.5	0.02011		
3.288288	2.925373		

paired WILCOXON				
	AudioOnly	Both	None	
Both	0.14	-	-	
None	0.32	0.14	-	
VisualsOnly	0.32	0.32	0.18	

Stimuli tempo and time judgment

Parameter: tempo | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo				
chi-2	df	p		
11.632	3	0.008755		

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]			
chi-2	df	p	
4.2724	2	0.1181	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]			
chi-2	df	p	
0.50583	2	0.7765	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo [filterBOTH]			
chi-2	df	p	
8.1283	2	0.01718	

paired WILCOXON				
	0	100	140	
100	0.384	-	-	
140	0.147	0.196	-	
180	0.025	0.023	0.147	

paired WILCOXON				
	100	140		
140	0.094	-		
180	0.017	0.251		

Correlations time judgment - estimation - performance

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized

PEARSON deltaTimePerception~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.28291486	0.0054709	-0.1417278	0.05915

PEARSON abs(deltaTimePerception)~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.0912122	0.2020339	0.0566321	0.4527

SPEARMAN deltaTimePerception~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
-0.1710288	0.02246	

SPEARMAN abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
0.0036190	0.9618	

SPEARMAN correctNormalized~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
0.1596657	0.03326	

Confounding effects of fatigue

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized, reportedFatigue

ANOVA correctNormalized~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
3.977	0.0477	

Anova deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
1.197	0.275	

Anova abs(deltaPerception)~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
0.924	0.338	

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
2-1	0.04617316	0.0004817	0.0918645	0.0476583

Spearman deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
-0.0615534	0.4144	

Spearman abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.1026692	0.1727	

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
-0.0381615	0.613	

Spearman correctNormalized~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.1566498	0.03678	

Confounding effects of trial index

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), correctNormalized, trialIndex

Pearson correctNormalized~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.01840973	0.2709667	0.1290243	0.08608

Pearson deltaTimePerception~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1292046	0.1648692	0.0182264	0.8092

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1003005	0.1932196	0.0474843	0.5291